

PHYSICS CONTRIBUTION

Analyzing Cardiorespiratory Motion and Its Dosimetric Effect on Stereotactic Arrhythmia Radio-Ablation: A STOPSTORM.eu Consortium Study

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Purpose: Stereotactic arrhythmia radio-ablation (STAR) is increasingly used to treat refractory ventricular tachycardia. The importance of cardiorespiratory motion during STAR is still poorly understood. We collected multicenter STOPSTORM.eu data to estimate cardiorespiratory motion and its dosimetric impact on STAR-deliveries.

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Methods and Materials: Data were collected from 61 ventricular tachycardia patients. Treatments were performed in free-breathing (FB) with an internal-target volume (FB:ITV) (25 patients), in FB with respiratory beam tracking (FB:TR) (11 patients), using abdominal compression (AC) (10 patients), or in deep inspiration breath-hold (BH) (15 patients). Reference computed tomography images were registered to all breathing/cardiac phases, and the resulting deformation vector fields were used to extract motion for target structures and auto-contoured cardiorespiratory structures (CSs). Additionally, CS were auto-contoured on all breathing/cardiac phases to extract motion independently. Inverse deformation vector fields were used to accumulate motion-adjusted dose distributions. Dose differences were estimated using the conformity index: $(V_{PTV25Gy})^2 / (V_{PTV} \cdot V_{25Gy})$, for planning target volume, and maximum and mean dose differences for CS.

Results: The median 95th percentile planning target volume motion was comparable between patients, with 6.0 mm (FB), 5.6 mm (AC), and 4.9 mm (BH). The left ventricle had the highest median 95th percentile motion out of all CS, with 6.8 mm (FB), 5.5 mm (AC), and 5.9 mm (BH). Estimated motion values were comparable between deformable image registration and auto-contouring (FB, 2.9-7.6 vs 3.1-8.5 mm; AC, 2.4-15.1 vs 3.0-9.0 mm; BH, 1.0-7.3 vs 2.4-6.7 mm). Median conformity index was reduced in the accumulated dose compared to the planned dose by: FB:ITV (-7.2%), AC (-14.1%), BH (-4.3%), and FB:TR (-1.3%). Mean CS dose increased by up to 2 Gy, and maximum dose increased by up to 1.2 Gy (excluding outliers). The largest dose differences were found for small CS.

Conclusions: Motion and its dosimetric effect have similar magnitudes between treatment setups. Motion findings were consistent between deformable image registration and auto-contouring. Only tracking significantly limited the dosimetric impact of motion. © 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Inc. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Introduction

Stereotactic arrhythmia radio-ablation (STAR) is increasingly used to treat refractory ventricular tachycardia (VT).^{1,2} The most common STAR treatment aims to deliver 25 Gy in a single fraction to the arrhythmia substrate, with maximum doses often reaching up to 40 Gy.²⁻⁴ Although STAR has shown promising clinical results, further research is required to optimize the treatment and improve its outcomes, as well as reduce the risk of (late) side effects.⁵⁻⁷ Among the unique challenges of STAR, cardiorespiratory motion (CRM) can lead to suboptimal targeting, and the dosimetric impact of CRM on the STAR delivery for VT patients is poorly understood. This is especially important considering the delivery of a high single dose, which can lead to severe toxicity if delivered outside the region of interest.^{6,7}

Several studies have investigated CRM, but most have a limited sample size or rely on data from healthy subjects or heart failure patients, which might be unsuitable surrogates for VT patients.⁸⁻¹¹ These studies have shown that the respiratory motion component is typically greater compared to the cardiac motion component.^{10,12} However, the observed cardiac motion component varies largely between studies.^{8-10,13} This is likely caused by different methods of analysis and large intersubject differences. Additionally, most studies are single center and, therefore, investigate a single respiratory management setup. There are no recommendations or considerations for the choice of a specific setup, and the treatment setup is usually center-specific based on the center's experience, preference, and availability. Therefore, data on CRM, including comparisons between treatment setups, are scarce.

Identifying distinct motion patterns and dosimetric effects per treatment setup may allow for tailored margin strategies, potentially improving target coverage and reducing toxicity. Alternatively, treatment margins might be

required on a personal level if CRM differs substantially between patients.^{9,14}

Beyond motion itself, CRM's impact on dose distribution is a key concern. Treatments must remain robust against motion displacements while minimizing excess radiation to healthy tissue. Limited, single-center research has been conducted on the effect of CRM on dose distributions in STAR.^{10,15}

In this research, we analyze CRM and its dosimetric effect in treatment setups with 4 different motion management techniques, namely free-breathing (FB) with an internal-target volume (FB:ITV), FB with respiratory beam tracking (FB:TR), abdominal compression (AC), and breath-hold (BH). We calculated the subject-specific motion for different cardiorespiratory structures (CSs) and the target structures to determine whether the motion is patient or setup-specific. Then, we accumulated the delivered dose and compared this to the planned dose. Finally, we compared the dose differences between treatment setups to find if any setup is more robust than the others.

Methods and Materials

Patient cohort

Ethical approval for data collection was obtained through the STOPSTORM European observational and prospective registry trial (University Hospital Zurich, Switzerland, BASEC 2021-01730) and local ethics review (University Medical Center Utrecht, Utrecht, The Netherlands).

Nine STOPSTORM.eu consortium centers provided clinical computed tomography (CT) scans, including motion, for 61 VT patients in total. The median (min-max) left ventricular ejection fraction of this group was 33.5% (17%-52%).

Table 1 Study population overview

Modality	FB:ITV	FB:TR	AC	BH
No. of patients	25	11	10	15
CT phases per patient	5-10	5-10	10	2
Mean PTV size (range), cc	148 (46-362)	52 (25-75)	65 (7-154)	62 (22-118)
Target locations (% of total) (lateral/inferior/apical/septal/basal)	28/4/32/28/8	27/9/18/45/0	10/0/30/40/20	33/20/20/20/7
Age, mean (range), y	69 (54-83)	67 (48-79)	74 (62-85)	66 (45-80)
Male sex	85%	91%	100%	93%

Abbreviations: AC = abdominal compression; BH = breath-hold; CT = computed tomography; FB:ITV = free-breathing: internal-target volume; FB:TR = free-breathing: tracking; PTV = planning target volume.

Most VT patients were treated in FB (36 patients, from which were treated in 25 FB:ITV and 11 in FB:TR), whereas others were treated in either AC (10 patients) or BH (15 patients). Patients treated in FB and AC had 4-dimensional (4D)-CT scans covering the respiratory cycle. However, the number of phases in which the respiratory cycle was divided differed per patient. The patients treated in BH had diastolic and systolic contrast CT scans available. Additionally, the anatomic region of the target was extracted based on electro-anatomical mapping (28% complete) data or visual inspection if electro-anatomical mapping was unavailable. An overview of these data can be found in [Table 1](#).

Motion analysis

We analyzed motion using 2 separate methods using either deformable image registration (DIR) or CSs auto-contouring. We selected a reference CT from the available motion phases for each patient. In FB or AC, the reference CT represented the phase that most closely matched the liver-lung interface of the planning CT, whereas for BH, it was always the diastolic contrast CT. Next, an openly available deep learning network was used to create CS contours on the planning CT.¹⁶ The planning target volume (PTV), as clinically created, and CS contours were used for motion analysis. The deformation vector field (DVF) (from planning CT to the reference phase) was applied to the structures and the dose file to warp them onto the reference phase. This was used as the static reference.

In the DIR motion estimation approach, the reference phase was deformably registered to the remaining CT phases (either the other breathing phases for FB and AC or the systolic phase for BH). DIR was performed using Elastix's^{17,18} SimpleElastix implementation. Most of the DIR settings came from Elastix automated parameter estimation per case; however, the registration cost function was changed to normalized cross-correlation, the number of spatial samples was increased to 10000, and the number of iterations was increased to 2000.

In the auto-contouring motion estimation approach, CS were inferred for all individual phases, and these contours

were compared to the static reference contours. This method circumvents possible inaccuracies around the implantable cardioverter–defibrillator (ICD) leads that exist using DIR.

Motion statistics were extracted for both DIR and auto-contouring motion approaches. In the DIR approach, the DVFs were (individually) convolved with the reference structures, and the 95th percentile motion per structure per phase was extracted. In the auto-contouring approach, the resulting contours per phase were compared to the contours in the reference phase based on the 95% Hausdorff distance. Additionally, the volume ratio (VR) was calculated between structures in the reference phase and their sum over the motion phases to extract the volume encompassed by structures over the motion cycle. The individual contours for DIR were created by warping the reference contour to the individual phases. Significant differences were tested using the Bonferroni-Holm–corrected Mann-Whitney *U* test, where *P*values <.05 indicated significance.¹⁹

Dosimetric analysis

Next, the dose was analyzed, as visualized in [Figure 1](#). Accumulating the delivered dose over the separate motion phases was done by first copying the reference dose to each individual motion phase and dividing it by the number of motion phases. Thereafter, the inverse of the DVF per motion phase was applied to the respective phase's dose distribution, and the resulting dose distributions were summed. Reference structure masks were used to extract the delivered dose, which was then compared to the planned doses. The comparison for the PTV was done based on the conformity index:

$$(V_{PTV25Gy})^2 / (V_{PTV} \cdot V_{25Gy})$$

where, $V_{PTV25Gy}$ is the overlapping volume between the PTV and the volume that receives the intended target dose. The CS dose was compared based on the mean (D_{mean}) and maximum dose (D_{max}), where $D_{0.01cc}$ is used as a surrogate

Fig. 1. Deformable image registration (DIR) motion estimation and dose accumulation workflow. The top row (imaging) displays how deformation vector fields (DVFs) are calculated. The middle row (motion) displays how the contour set is applied to the DVFs to estimate motion. The bottom row (dose) displays how the DVFs (and their inverse) are used to calculate the accumulated dose and extract dose parameters. *Abbreviation:* CT = computed tomography.

for maximum dose. To investigate the robustness of dose differences for small CS, they were expanded using mean surface distance (MSD), as extracted from previous data, whereafter the dosimetric comparison was repeated.¹⁶ The used rounded MSD values (in mm) were 5 (aortic valve), 3 (mitral valve [MV]), 7 (pulmonic valve), 6 (tricuspid valve), 12 (left anterior descending coronary artery [LAD]), 14 (left circumflex coronary artery [LCX]), 4 (left main coronary artery), and 15 (right coronary artery [RCA]).

For patients treated using tracking, the delivery was simulated using the median shift of the PTV. Thereafter, this median shift was subtracted from every DVF point before inverting the DVFs to simulate the center of mass compensation. The remainder of the workflow was the same as for the other scenarios.

Extension to 5-dimensional data

A single patient had both respiratory 4DCT and cardiac 4DCT available and was previously included in the FB:ITV group. In addition, this patient was analyzed in the 5-dimensional (5D) data set to provide better comparability of cardiac and respiratory motion. Here, each respiratory phase was used to deform the dose; thereafter, each respiratory phase was deformed to the diastolic phase before applying the cardiac DVFs. Then, the individual doses were summed to create one accumulated 5D dose. Alternatively, 4D dose accumulation was performed using the same methodology as in FB:ITV and BH treatment setups. The outcomes of the separate motion analyses were compared. The static dose in the separate FB:ITV and BH scenarios was

compared to investigate possible registration-induced differences.

Validation of DIR

The performance of the DIR was evaluated by comparing the structural similarity index measure before and after registration to the reference. Possible DVF edge errors were circumvented by evaluating the images with a field of view around the heart.

The Jacobian determinant was calculated per structure for each DVF in the motion analysis. In addition to calculating compression/expansion, the Jacobian determinant was used to quantify possible DIR errors, which would be pointed out by large (>2.5) or small (<0.4) values.²⁰⁻²² This range (0.4 to 2.5) was used to mask structures and generate a motion field with reduced errors. Nevertheless, unrealistic maximum motion still existed in the DVFs; therefore, the 95th percentile largest motion was extracted instead of the full maximum motion. Besides the Jacobian determinant itself, the SD of the Jacobian determinant was retrieved to inspect the stability of the deformation within structures before masking. Additionally, the warped contours from the DIR were compared to contours created by auto-contouring to assess contour consistency. This comparison was made based on Dice score (DSC) and MSD.

Results

Motion analysis

Registration of the planning CT to the reference phase CT scans was successful, as indicated by an increase in the structural similarity index measure (FB: from 0.82 to 0.93, AC: from 0.85 to 0.94, BH: from 0.73 to 0.85). The comparison of deformed contours with auto-contoured contours revealed good or excellent overlap for the 4 chambers, with median DSCs of 0.89 (FB), 0.90 (AC), and

0.83 (BH). Additionally, the MSD was found to be small with 1.8 mm (FB), 1.6 mm (AC), and 3.3 mm (BH). Smaller CS contours, on the other hand, were less consistent between the 2 contouring methods when quantified in terms of DSC (Fig. 2). In contrast, the small CS MSDs were comparable and below 5 mm for nearly all structures. The results for the BH group were consistently worse for nearly all CS. Using the DIR method to estimate motion showed vulnerability to image artifacts, mainly caused by the ICD leads, as visual assessment of warped images confirmed correct alignment. This was reflected in unrealistically high motion, with some findings over 100 mm. Therefore, the 95th percentile of motion was calculated, which can be seen in Figure 3A. Patients treated in BH showed the lowest median 95th percentile PTV motion (4.9 mm), but this was not significantly different from either FB (6.0 mm) or AC (5.6 mm). The CS that showed the highest 95th percentile motion was the left

ventricle (LV) in each treatment setup, which showed the most motion during FB (median, 6.8 mm). However, this was not significantly different from the other setups (median AC: 5.5 mm, median BH: 5.9 mm).

The VR using DIR showed the largest relative increase in PTV for the AC group (median 1.71), whereas the FB group (median 1.40) and BH group (median 1.22) were lower (Fig. 3B). However, this is not only a motion effect, as the absolute PTVs of the FB group were, on average, 124% larger than those of the AC group (Table 1). The median VRs of the LV using DIR were 1.21 (FB), 1.23 (AC), and 1.04 (BH). These are lower compared to the PTV VR, which is likely because the absolute volume of the LV is larger than the PTV, although the motion is similar (Fig. 3B). The VRs of the other 3 chambers were comparable to that of the LV using DIR, with values in the range of 1.27 to 1.32 (FB), 1.27 to 1.28 (AC), and 1.06 to 1.15 (BH). The highest VR was found for the coronary arteries in each of the treatment setups, with median VR values between 2.78 to 3.86 (FB), 2.75 to 4.30 (AC), and 1.58 to 1.82 (BH) using DIR. In each group, the highest median VR was found for the RCA. The median VRs of the valves were more stable and ranged from 1.60 to 2.25 (FB), 1.58 to 2.37 (AC), and 1.21 to 1.43 (BH) using DIR.

The median Jacobian determinant values for both the PTV and the LV showed values close to 1, meaning that the volume of structures was similar between motion phases (Fig. 3C). Additionally, the SD of the Jacobian determinant showed that limited unplausible deformations took place, with median SD of the Jacobian determinants: PTV (0.18, 0.55, and 0.14 for FB, AC, and BH, respectively), left atrium (0.14, 0.23, and 0.11 for FB, AC, and BH, respectively), and LV (0.24, 0.59, and 0.18 for FB, AC, and BH, respectively), suggesting relatively uniform geometric deformations. However, this was not the case for all structures, eg, the median SD of the Jacobian determinants for the right ventricle (RV) were much higher in comparison (0.55, 1.41, and 0.38 for FB, AC, and BH, respectively). Therefore, the motion estimation using DVFs might be less suitable for the RV.

Using the auto-contouring method to estimate motion information showed similar LV motion with median 95% Hausdorff distances of 6.7 mm (FB), 4.8 mm (AC), and 5.6 mm (BH). Nevertheless, a Bonferroni-Holm-corrected Mann-Whitney *U* test revealed significant differences in the distribution between the 2 methods in the FB and AC group (*P*-values $<.05$). However, the range of motion values calculated for all CS using the separate methods was similar overall. Median CS motion in the FB group ranged from 2.9 to 7.6 mm (DVF) versus 3.1 to 8.5 mm (auto-contouring), in the AC group it ranged from 2.4 to 15.1 mm (DVF) versus 3.0 to 9.0 mm (auto-contouring), and in the BH group it ranged from 1.0 to 7.3 mm (DVF) versus 2.4 to 6.7 mm (auto-contouring). Overall, the auto-contouring approach produced lower values.

Furthermore, the VR values that were found using auto-contouring were comparable to those of DIR. The median VRs for the LV were 1.21 (FB), 1.21 (AC), and 1.03 (BH),

Fig. 2. Dice score (DSC) (A) and mean surface distance (B) comparison between warped and auto-contoured structures for all individual motion phases per treatment setup. *Abbreviations:* Inf = inferior; LAD = left anterior descending coronary artery; LCX = left circumflex coronary artery; LM = left main coronary artery; MSD = mean surface distance; RCA = right coronary artery; Sup = superior.

which were also comparable to the VRs of the other chambers at 1.26 to 1.32 (FB), 1.17 to 1.26 (AC), and 1.05 to 1.12 (BH). Also using the auto-contouring approach, the coronary arteries had the highest median VR with values ranging from 3.03 to 4.03 (FB), 2.72 to 4.34 (AC), and 1.49 to 1.84 (BH). The RCA had the largest VR, except in the FB group, where it was the second-largest after the LCX. The VR of the valves using the auto-contouring approach, 1.76 to 2.53

(FB), 1.47 to 2.32 (AC), and 1.16 to 1.79 (BH), was also comparable to the results using the DIR approach.

Dosimetric analysis

The planned median Dmax for the PTVs were 31.8 Gy (FB: ITV), 28.9 Gy (AC), 29.4 Gy (BH), and 29.7 Gy (FB:TR).

Fig. 3. Display of deformable image registration (DIR)-based results for the 95th percentile motion (A), the volume ratio (B), and the mean Jacobian determinant (C) for the planning target volume (PTV) and left ventricle (LV).

The planned median Dmean values for the PTVs were 27.5 Gy (FB:ITV), 26.5 Gy (AC), 24.4 Gy (BH), and 27.1 Gy (FB:TR). The planned median conformity indices were 0.69 (FB:ITV), 0.57 (AC), 0.74 (BH), and 0.61 (FB:TR). These planned median conformity indices experienced slight changes due to warping the dose distribution from the planning CT to the static reference CT with median differences of 0.001 (−0.1%, FB:ITV), −0.02 (−2.7%, AC), −0.01 (−1.47%, BH), and −0.01 (−1.0%, FB:TR). The conformity index differences due to motion were larger for the FB:ITV, AC, and BH group (accumulated minus reference) with medians of −0.05 (−7.2%), −0.08 (−14.1%), and −0.03 (−4.3%), respectively (Fig. 4A). These groups showed no significant differences between them. The FB:TR group showed minimal differences between accumulated and reference conformity index (median: −0.01 [−1.3%]), but this was not significantly different from the other groups.

The dose differences for the LV were small in all treatment setups, with the mean dose differences

<1.4 Gy, and maximum dose differences <2.0 Gy (Fig. 4B). The FB:ITV group showed the largest dose differences, which is in line with the largest LV motion being found in that group. In the CS dose differences, only the LV maximum dose in the FB:TR group was significantly more stable compared to the other structures (P values ≤ 0.02). The largest mean and maximum dose differences for CS were found in the small CS, specifically the LAD (FB:ITV and AC), MV (FB:TR), and LCX (BH). The only exception was the difference in maximum dose in the FB:TR group, which was found in the RV. Mean dose differences for these small CS were relatively minor, with only a few outliers with differences beyond 2 Gy. Valves showed the largest differences

in maximum dose, with values up to 4 Gy, specifically the MV (FB:ITV and BH) and pulmonic valve (AC) (Fig. 4C). When using the expanded contours for the small CS, only minor dose differences due to motion were observed. Median dose differences were below 1 Gy for both maximum and mean dose, with only a single outlier beyond 4 Gy (maximum dose to the MV in the FB:ITV scenario). The largest dose differences per treatment setup can be found in Table E1.

Motion-induced dose differences between the different motion groups were comparable. However, initial dose distributions differed notably. The mean doses to CS were in the range of 0.62 to 11.38 Gy (FB:ITV), 0.68 to 8.72 Gy (FB:TR), 1.06 to 10.61 Gy (AC), and 0.20 to 8.42 Gy

(BH). The maximum doses to the CS were in the range of 2.44 to 30.37 Gy (FB:ITV), 1.48 to 27.19 Gy (FB:TR), 4.55 to 29.15 Gy (AC), and 0.97 to 27.54 Gy (BH). Further planned doses to CS can be found in Tables E2 and E3. The differences in planned dose might be explained by the PTV size. The average cardiac target volume to PTV ratio was much larger for the FB:ITV group (6.6) compared to FB:TR (2.4) and BH (2.1), whereas these data were lacking for the AC group.

5D motion and dose analysis

The patient with 5D data showed larger motion due to breathing compared to cardiac motion for the PTV, with median 95th percentile PTV motions of 6.3 mm (respiratory) and 4.8 mm (cardiac). Interestingly, the LV showed a higher 95th percentile motion for the cardiac motion

Fig. 4. Display of the dosimetric differences between the reference and motion-accumulated dose. Free-breathing + tracking shows the least differences. *Abbreviations:* ITV = internal-target volume; LAD = left anterior descending coronary artery; LCX = left circumflex coronary artery; LV = left ventricle; MV = mitral valve; PTV = planning target volume, PV = pulmonic valve; RV = right ventricle.

(median 7.7 mm) compared to the respiratory motion (median 5.3 mm). This corresponded to the magnitude of their respective mean Jacobian determinants of 1.13 (cardiac) and 0.97 (respiratory). However, deformations of the respiratory motion cycle were less stable, as found from their LV Jacobian determinant SD of 0.25 (cardiac) versus 0.85 (respiratory). Nevertheless, the VR was much larger for the respiratory motion cycle (VR: 1.49 for PTV and 1.28 for LV) compared to the cardiac motion cycle (VR: 1.04 for PTV and 1.02 for LV). The dose comparison between the 5D accumulated dose and the 4D respiratory dose revealed small maximum dose differences for the large CS (between -1.06 and $+0.74$ Gy, with positive values for higher dose in the 5D scenario). The mean dose differences were somewhat larger, especially for the RV (-3.74 Gy). Interestingly, the conformity index dropped severely (-0.43 in the 5D scenario), but the PTV was near the ICD lead and thus its artifact. The largest dose differences were found for small structures, with differences in mean dose up to -2.86 Gy (LAD) and differences in maximum dose up to -12.87 Gy (LAD). However, most of the dose differences were small, with mean dose differences averaged across all CS of -0.65 Gy and mean maximum dose differences of -1.39 Gy. The dose analysis showed a slight increase of conformity index (0.02, or 2.66%) in the cardiac motion scenario, whereas the respiratory motion led to a relatively larger decrease of conformity index (-0.09 , or -14.25%). However, the conformity index in the reference phase for the 2 motion cycles was slightly different and 0.015 higher in the respiratory

motion scenario. In both scenarios, the LV showed an increased mean dose (0.34 Gy during respiration and 0.41 Gy during cardiac motion) but a slightly decreased maximum dose (-0.32 Gy during respiration and -0.12 Gy during cardiac motion). The largest maximum dose difference during the cardiac motion was found for the LCX ($+2.64$ Gy), whereas it was found for the LAD (-1.00 Gy) during respiratory motion. Reference phase dose parameters differed, as the same treatment plan was deformed to different reference phases; the largest difference was found for the LAD with a mean dose difference of 3.62 Gy and a maximum dose difference of 11.98 Gy (both higher in the cardiac analysis). Interestingly, the 5D dose for the LV and LAD closely resembled the dose of the respiratory scenario, whereas it was also warped to the diastolic reference phase. The comparison of the different dose scenarios for the PTV, LV, and LAD can be found in [Figure 5](#).

Discussion

In this multi-institutional study, we were the first to investigate CRM and its dosimetric effect on targets and CS across 4 different motion management strategies in STAR. We developed 2 independent methods to estimate subject-specific motion for the PTV and CS, which revealed motion to be patient-specific rather than setup-specific. Finally, we showed the dosimetric impact of this motion by comparing the planned dose with the motion-accumulated dose.

Fig. 5. Dose-volume histogram for the planned, reference, and accumulated dose for free-breathing, cardiac, and 5-dimensional (5D) motion scenarios. *Abbreviation:* PTV = planning target volume.

Patients in the FB group showed the largest motion for their targets as well as their CS, but this was not significantly different from the AC and BH groups. Additionally, inter-subject motion variability was large, even within one treatment setup group. Also, the left ventricular ejection fraction was highly variable but low overall (median 33.5%). The magnitude of the motion found in this study (median 95th percentile PTV motion, 4.9 to 6.0 mm) is comparable to other studies.^{8-11,23,24} Furthermore, the VR that we found (median VR PTV, 1.22 to 1.71) is in the range reported by both Li et al.¹⁰ and in the review by Stevens et al.²³

The mean Jacobian determinant values close to 1 indicated that structures stay approximately the same size. However, some structures had a large SD. In all treatment setups, the SD was the largest for the superior vena cava, the right atrium, the RV, and the pulmonic valve (only in the FB and AC groups). These structures have in common that they are part of the most common ICD lead trajectory. Thus, inaccuracies in DIR might be caused by the metal artifacts of the ICD leads. Masking the structures using the Jacobian determinant between 0.4 and 2.5 did not completely resolve the problem, as was revealed by the unfeasibly large maximum motion. Retrieving the 95th percentile of the motion further improved the stability of the outcomes at the expense of an apparent reduction in maximum motion. Studies focused on MRI also reported errors due to ICD artifacts, but no solutions.^{8,9} To our knowledge, no additional action to limit or circumvent these inaccuracies has been explicitly taken by others researching CT data. Future research should focus on finding reliable methods to investigate motion in the

presence of artifacts. The metal artifacts had less impact on auto-contouring because the training data also contained metal artifacts. Therefore, it was used as an alternative to extract motion. However, the downside of auto-contouring is that there is no appropriate method to auto-contour the target structure; thus, it cannot be used to investigate its motion. Estimating motion using 2 independent methods, DIR and auto-contouring, was explored here for the first time. However, a clear preference for one method over the other has not been found in this research, as a ground truth is lacking. Manual contouring would be a less-than-ideal way to create a ground truth, as it is very time-consuming and suffers from interobserver variability that is nearly equal to the magnitude of the extracted motion in this study. Additionally, our auto-contouring versus DIR deformed contour methods (4 chamber median DSC ≥ 0.83) produced results similar to those in the comparison of manual contours versus DIR deformed contours, as shown by Harms et al.²⁴ In our study, the MSD between contours created by the DIR warping and auto-contouring methods on a single phase is low, even for small CS. Furthermore, motion in the range of millimeters is only 1 or a few voxels, which is potentially below the detection threshold of manual observers.

The most stable conformity index was found for the FB:TR group (median difference of -0.01 or -1.3%) due to the motion being compensated, whereas the differences in conformity index for FB:ITV (-0.05 or -7.2%), AC (-0.08 or -14.1%), and BH (-0.03 or -4.3%) were more pronounced. Furthermore, the BH group has the smallest target volumes

and the smallest margins (indicated by the highest original conformity index) and, thereby, the steepest dose gradients, which makes BH treatment more susceptible to residual motion. The reduced conformity index we found is somewhat smaller than that reported by Li et al,¹⁰ but this could be due to several factors, including target size and treatment planning considerations. Although limited to a single case, the 5D analysis illustrates how simultaneous cardiac and respiratory motion can compound dose variability, reinforcing the need for multidimensional motion modeling in STAR. The 5D case highlighted that the initial conformity index not only differs between cases but also within a case, due to warping to a specific reference phase. In general, this warping had a limited effect on the conformity index (<1.5%). Nevertheless, this inequality in dose distributions complicates the comparison of the dosimetric impact of cardiac motion with that of respiratory motion. Regarding the PTV dose, the FB scenario showed a larger decrease in target coverage compared to the planned dose. However, in both the motion scenarios, the target coverage was similar to their respective reference coverage. The 5D scenario revealed a stronger decrease in target coverage compared to the individual motion scenarios. This showed that a combination of cardiac and respiratory motion may be needed for optimal treatment planning. Additionally, motion mitigation strategies to account for target coverage may be unaware of the dose effect for CS. However, this might differ on a patient-by-patient basis, as this analysis was limited to one data set; thus, further 5D research is required.

The mean dose to the LV was stable for all treatment setups, and stability was increased in FB:TR, AC, and BH setups compared to FB:ITV. The maximum dose was slightly less stable, as one would expect, and also benefited from motion reduction or compensation methods. The dose differences for the LV were smaller than expected, as it showed the highest median 95th percentile motion out of the CS. The dose differences we reported are comparable to those reported by Li et al.¹⁰ The dose differences outlined in this work are up to 4 Gy, which can have a significant impact on treatment plans. Larger dose differences were found for small CS, explained by the fact that their motion is larger relative to their size. Reducing respiratory motion, either by compression or BH, showed limited to no impact in keeping the dose to the small CS more similar to the planned dose. Tracking did reduce the dose differences for both small and large CS. However, tracking here has been simulated using a simplified translation shift approach. The actual impact of tracking might differ depending on intrafraction motion and the correlation between the tracked point and the structures of interest. In our analyses, we assumed the motion described in the 4D images to remain valid throughout the delivery. The initial dose received by CS is not highlighted here, as there are no standardized dose limits for CS in STAR; thus, surpassing such limits due to motion cannot be investigated. Once CS dose limits become available, the dose inaccuracy due to motion should be considered during treatment planning with concepts such as planning risk

volumes (PRVs). Motion becomes increasingly important when steep dose gradients are present, such as when protons are used for STAR. STAR using protons is currently being further developed, but active motion mitigation is advisable, and planning strategies should be robust, with motion margins for both (potential) organs at risk as well as the target.^{25,26} Additionally, recent retrospective studies investigating the possibility of using protons for STAR have shown a reduction in organs at risk dose compared to photon STAR.^{27,28}

A limitation is that the AC and BH treatment setup groups contained data from mainly one center. For the AC group, all cases came from a single center, and for the BH group, 12 of 15 cases came from one center. Although this aligns the treatment methodology and, therefore, makes comparisons of findings within those groups easier, it does not fully reflect the range of values that might be present in different clinics using a similar treatment setup. The different treatment setups showed different planned mean doses, which were in line with their PTV, where larger volumes showed larger highest mean doses to CS, except that the FB:TR was slightly higher than BH group. A similar trend was found for the maximum doses to CS. Although motion-limiting treatment setups did not show increased similarity between planning and accumulated dose, the reduction in PTV and the resulting reduction in dose to CS could be beneficial for possible late toxicities. However, treatment planning choices between different plans have a large influence, requiring further consensus.²⁹

Another possibly impactful parameter is the exact anatomic location of the target inside the heart. A future study looking into motion per anatomic subregion and investigating the possibility of treatment setup preference for such subregions is recommended.

CRM is particularly relevant for small structures such as the coronary arteries and valves, where variations in dose accumulation could influence the risk of late toxicities. Thus, a more comprehensive approach to motion management in STAR could be beneficial, particularly when high-dose gradients intersect mobile CS. This approach could consist of treatment plans robust for target motion and the use of PRVs. Additionally, further research should assess whether simplified methods, such as combining separate 4D cardiac and respiratory motion models, could approximate the effects of 5D motion without significantly increasing computational complexity. PRV dose constraints should be explored to determine whether specific substructures require additional caution. Future clinical studies are needed to assess the impact of cardiac motion on long-term treatment outcomes to determine whether these dosimetric differences translate into measurable toxicity risks.

Conclusions

Our analysis demonstrated that CRM in STAR patients is patient-specific rather than treatment setup-specific, with

FB cases exhibiting the largest motion but without significant differences compared to AC and BH. Tracking-based delivery proved to be effective in mitigating the dosimetric impact of respiratory motion, yielding the smallest deviations between planned and accumulated doses. Dose deviations were most pronounced for smaller CS, which can move in and out of the high-dose region even with relatively small motion. This highlights the potential risk of localized dose hot spots to radiosensitive CS. The 5D case analysis underscored the importance of integrating both respiratory and cardiac motion in future motion management strategies and dose accumulation studies, but further research into 5D analyses is warranted. Future studies should validate motion-compensated dose delivery, explore the clinical relevance of CSs dose variations, and refine margin strategies based on patient-specific motion patterns to optimize STAR planning.

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